

EUROPEAN CO-ORDINATED QUADRANGLE MAPPING OF MERCURY

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ABSTRACT

MESSENGER data are being used to create 1:3M quadrangle geologic maps of Mercury [1], in preparation for BepiColombo [2]. Maps H02-H05 have already been published [3-6] and others are in progress [e.g. 7-12] or scheduled with the exception of H01 (Figure 1). Mapping uses 166 mpp mosaics, and digitization is at a scale of 1:300k. The mapper for each quadrangle maps a 5° overlap with adjacent quadrangles, and it will be possible to produce a globally merged product. Mapping protocols follow the mapping standards document of the Planmap project [13], which are modelled closely on the USGS equivalent.

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Figure Caption: The status of European quadrangle mapping on Mercury. Maps in the equatorial and southern rows are not yet published. H10 and H14 are expected in 2020. Green = in progress, blue = scheduled.